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Cultivating Happiness through Wisdom Education: A Pathway to Peace and Harmony

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Abstract

Present world is facing numerous challenges ranging from as simple as unavailability of basic living resources to complex ones as increasing wars and deterioration of peace. Moreover, with constantly increasing rate of work related pressure, societal disharmony and psychological inabilities to bring about balance in life, individuals today are more prone to anxiety, stress, brain fog and chaos. There is a dire need of cultivating happiness. The study has four objectives that include (1) the higher education learners' views on material sources of happiness (2) their viewpoint on happiness in terms of feelings (3) their views on correlation of happiness and wisdom and (4) the suggestive ways to achieve happiness through wisdom education. The qualitative data was collected through three sessions of focus group discussion. The obtained data was transcribed into codes and themes which were then analysed by content analysis and thematic analysis. It was found that the higher education learners consider good food, spending time with friends, pursuing a hobby, fun activities, success, wealth and relationships as external sources of happiness. They associate contentment, joy, pleasure, sense of achievement and personal growth and being at peace as the feelings associated with happiness. They find that the traits like emotional intelligence, problem solving ability, positive thinking, creativity, communication skills and ability to learn from mistakes and failures are those components of wisdom that can highly affect the achievement of happiness by a person. The measures suggested by the higher education learners for imparting wisdom education for happiness are extra-curricular activities, community visits and group projects. These may help in enhancing happiness both during the process and as the product (outcome).

Keywords: *Wisdom, wisdom education, happiness, peace*

Introduction

Present world faces many problems in society both in micro and macro perspectives and its increasing complexity is making the scenario much worse for existence of a happy and content world. The pursuit of happiness and overall well-being has become a pressing concern for individuals. Despite technological advancements, socio-economic growth and ease in access to education and other basic amenities of life, the society still struggles to cope with stress,

anxiety, expectations and responsibilities in interpersonal relationships and other societal and work-related pressures. This has given rise to a feeling of discontentment and disconnect with the outer world. The situation recognizes a need for cultivating wisdom as a pathway to happiness. The society is acknowledging the importance of wisdom for the prevalence of peace and harmony among individuals. According to Thomas Equinas, “Of all the pursuits open to men, the search for wisdom is most perfect, more sublime, more profitable, and more full of joy”

UNESCO Bangkok launched the Happy Schools Project in 2014 and proposed a Happy School Framework. The framework suggests that education systems need to shift away from traditional measures and focus on diversity of talents and intelligence that calls for taking into consideration the values, strengths and competencies of students. These will thereby enhance student happiness. The wisdom education of higher education students plays a vital role in imbibing a value system both in present as well as futuristic perspectives. By cultivating wisdom, students can develop a deeper understanding of themselves and the world around them. They get acquainted with their inner conflicts that result into incoherent behaviour outside. When individuals reach this level of self-awareness, they become more compassionate and empathetic towards themselves as well as others. Wisdom education can help individuals to understand that happiness is not a product of outer stimuli but is rather an inner state of self.

The way to develop a positive attitude towards one and another has been explained in the Bhagvad Gita by Lord Krishna while teaching Arjuna to help him find the solution to his sorrow, he states that the fundamental problem of a human mind is that it is unpredictable. The human mind is in a state of constant conflict. It is not just an ancient problem but finds its place in today’s world too. This mental state arises due to an underlying belief that one is inadequate which gives rise to a persistent feeling of “want” in all aspects of life. This constant desire of being different from what one already is gives rise to an approach of contrasting beliefs in all human undertakings. The mind just becomes a battlefield of conflicting ideas. A person becomes self critical and reflects it in other human interactions too. This leads to a constant state of competition, inadequacy and misery. Lord Krishna teaches Arjuna to be his adequate self by recognizing and accepting one’s own strengths and weaknesses, and finding contentment and happiness within oneself.

Bangen et al. (2013) reviewed the empirical definitions of wisdom and its most common subcomponents. According to the study, the wisdom sub-components that have been acknowledged by a majority of researchers are social decision making, pro-social values, reflection and acknowledgement of uncertainty. Research has consistently shown that wisdom is a key factor in promoting happiness, well-being, and life satisfaction (Ardelt, 2003; Baltes & Staudinger, 2000; Sternberg, 1990). Wisdom education, in particular, has been identified as a promising approach to cultivating wisdom and promoting positive outcomes (Ferrari & Potworowski, 2008). Wisdom education involves the intentional cultivation of wisdom through teaching, learning, and practice, and has been shown to promote wisdom, happiness, and well-being in both children and adults (Ferrari & Potworowski, 2008).

Studies have also highlighted the importance of emotional intelligence, self-awareness,

and mindfulness in promoting wisdom and happiness (Goleman, 1995; Langer, 1989; Salovey & Mayer, 1990). These factors are critical components of wisdom education, and have been shown to promote positive outcomes such as increased happiness, life satisfaction, and well-being (Ardelt, 2003; Baltes & Staudinger, 2000). Furthermore, research has also emphasized the importance of cultivating a sense of purpose, meaning, and direction in life, as well as promoting positive relationships and social connections (Seligman, 2011; Diener et al., 2000).

Despite extensive research of importance and positive outcomes of wisdom education there is still a need to conduct more studies on impact of wisdom education on promoting happiness, well-being and peace. This study aims to contribute to this knowledge gap by exploring the relationship between wisdom education and happiness, with a particular focus on the role of wisdom in promoting peace and harmony. By examining the experiences and perspectives of higher education learners the study aims to provide insights into the ways in which wisdom education can promote positive outcomes and contribute to a more peaceful and harmonious world.

Methodology

This study has four objectives to know the higher education learners' viewpoint on the material sources of happiness, to know the higher education learners' viewpoint on happiness in terms of feelings, to probe the higher education learners' viewpoint on correlation of wisdom and happiness and to suggest the ways of imparting wisdom education to promote happiness. The study employed a qualitative research approach, using focus group discussions (FGDs) as the primary method of data collection for the first three objectives and thought experiment for the fourth objective. The FGDs were conducted among a group of higher education learners, who were recruited through a combination of purposive and snowball sampling techniques. The participants were selected based on their interest in the topic of wisdom education and their willingness to engage in open and honest discussions about their experiences and perspectives.

Three sessions of FGDs were conducted, each of duration of 60-90 minutes. The sessions were conducted online to facilitate ease in availability of all participants at the same time and extracting more honest responses from the participants as they were participating from their own comfortable environment. The discussions were facilitated by a trained moderator, who used a semi-structured interview guide to explore the participants' thoughts, feelings, and experiences related to wisdom education and its impact on happiness and well-being. The FGDs were video-recorded by consent of the participants and lasted for approximately 60-90 minutes each. The recordings were then transcribed and transcript data was obtained.

The data obtained from the FGDs were analyzed using content analysis, a qualitative research technique that involves systematically coding and categorizing the data to identify patterns, themes, and meanings. The analysis was conducted in several stages, beginning with an initial review of the transcript data to identify preliminary themes and patterns. The data were then coded and categorized using a coding framework that was developed based on the research

questions and objectives. The coding framework consisted of several categories and subcategories, including wisdom education, happiness, well-being, peace, harmony, and personal growth.

The coded data were then analyzed using a thematic analysis approach, which involved identifying and interpreting the themes and patterns that emerged from the data. The themes were identified based on their frequency, intensity, and relevance to the research questions and objectives.

Analysis And Discussion

The analysis was conducted using a combination of inductive and deductive approaches, with the researcher moving back and forth between the data and the literature to identify and interpret the themes and patterns. The results of the analysis are presented in the following section, where the themes and patterns that emerged from the data are discussed in detail.

Table 1: Analysis of codes on “materials sources of happiness”

S.No.	Material sources of happiness (in terms of codes and themes)	Approximate percentage of participants in agreement
1	Good food	>50
2	Quality time with friends	>50
3	Fun activities	>50
4	Success	>50
5	Wealth	<50
6	Family is proud of me/ relationships	>50

The data suggests that a majority of participants (over 50%) agree that good food, quality time with friends, fun activities, success and having a family that is proud of them, positive relationships are all important sources of happiness. Many participants consider time well spent in exciting activities bring about happiness. Some participants also believe that doing something brings wealth and success brings utmost happiness as they are the driving forces of life. They also believe when the daily routine tasks of everyday are done effectively and efficiently, they also bring a pleasurable feeling.

It is note-worthy that the data does not provide a ranking or prioritization of the different material sources of happiness. Therefore, it is not possible to determine which sources of happiness are most important to the participants. However, the data does suggest that all six categories are widely recognized as important sources of happiness.

Table 2: Analysis of codes on “happiness in terms of feelings”

S.No.	Happiness in terms of Feelings (in terms of codes and themes)	Approximate percentage of participants in agreement (>50% or <50%)
1	Contentment	>50
2	When I am at peace	>50
3	Joy	>50
4	Pleasure	>50
5	Sense of achievement and personal growth	>50

The data presented in Table 2 provides an analysis of the codes related to “happiness in terms of feelings” among a group of participants. The data is organized into five categories, each representing a different feeling associated with happiness as are suggested by the participants. The approximate percentage of participants in agreement with each category is also provided. The data suggests that a majority of participants (over 50%) agree that contentment, being at peace, joy, pleasure, and a sense of achievement and personal growth are all important feelings associated with happiness. High percentage of being at peace suggests that a sense of calm and tranquility is a crucial aspect of happiness. Enjoyment and one’s competence are also found to be important aspect of happiness. Overall, the data suggests that happiness is a multifaceted concept that encompasses a range of feelings, including contentment, peace, joy, pleasure, and a sense of achievement and personal growth.

Table 3: Analysis of codes on “correlation of happiness and wisdom”

S.No.	Wisdom traits that are related to happiness (in terms of codes and themes)	Approximate percentage of participants in agreement (>50% or <50%)
1	Emotional intelligence	>50
2	Problem solving ability	>50

3	Positive thinking	>50
4	Creativity	<50
5	Communication skills	>50
6	Learning from mistakes and failures	>50

The data presented in Table 3 provides an analysis of the codes related to the correlation of happiness and wisdom among a group of participants. The data is organized into six categories, each representing a different wisdom trait that is related to happiness. The approximate percentage of participants in agreement with each category is also provided. Overall, the data suggests that a majority of participants (over 50%) agree that emotional intelligence, problem-solving ability, positive thinking, communication skills, and learning from mistakes and failures are all important wisdom traits that are related to happiness. The high percentage of agreement on emotional intelligence (over 50%) suggests that the ability to recognize and understand emotions in oneself and others is a key wisdom trait that is related to happiness. This is consistent with research in positive psychology, which suggests that emotional intelligence is a critical component of happiness and well-being (Furham & Petrides, 2003; Guerra-Bustamante, León-del-Barco, Yuste-Tosina, López-Ramos & Mendo-Lázaro, 2019 ; Biswas, 2022). The finding that over 50% of participants associate happiness with problem-solving ability suggests that the ability to effectively navigate challenges and difficulties is also an important wisdom trait that is related to happiness. This is consistent with research on resilience and coping, which suggests that the ability to effectively manage stress and adversity is essential for happiness and well-being. The high percentage of agreement on positive thinking (over 50%) suggests that having a optimistic outlook and attitude is also an important wisdom trait that is related to happiness. This is consistent with research on positive psychology, which suggests that positive thinking and attitude are critical components of happiness and well-being (Catalino, Algoe & Fredrickson, 2014) . The finding that less than 50% participants associate happiness with creativity suggests that creativity may not be as strongly related to happiness as other wisdom traits. However, this does not mean that creativity is not important for happiness, but rather that it may be a more complex relationship. The high percentage of agreement on communication skills (over 50%) suggests that the ability to effectively communicate with others is also an important wisdom trait that is related to happiness. This is consistent with research on social relationships and communication, which suggests that effective communication is essential for building and maintaining strong social relationships, which are critical for happiness and well-being (Ahmad & Chowdhury, 2022). Finally, the finding that over 50% of participants associate happiness with learning from mistakes and failures suggests that the ability to learn and grow from mistakes and failures is also an important wisdom trait that is related to happiness. This is consistent with research on resilience and coping, which suggests that the ability to learn and grow from adversity

is essential for happiness and well-being (Polatcý, Antalyalý, Alparslan, *et. al.*, 2023)

The measures suggested by the higher education learners includes more involvement of students in extra-curricular activities, community visits and group projects that can prove to be crucial for wisdom development and these are the methods that also include the material sources of happiness that were suggested by the students like spending time with friends etc. These measures can be researched further and an effective module for cultivating happiness through wisdom education can be proposed.

Conclusion

It is indicated by the study that cultivating wisdom through wisdom education can play a vital role in promoting happiness. Wisdom can effectively help individuals to navigate through difficult life situations and achieve happiness in the complex scenarios one faces on everyday basis. Methods like extra-curricular activities, community visits and group projects can prove to be effective ways to impart wisdom which will result in happiness both during process and the product. This will result in a more peaceful and harmonious society where individuals are compassionate, understanding and empathetic towards one another and can achieve a constant state of calmness inside their mind.

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